

**ANALYSIS OF MONETARY POLICY, CREDIT MARKET AND LENDING RATES
AMONG COMMERCIAL BANKS IN KENYA**

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With banks being the major avenue that the CBK relies on to execute monetary policy, the paper sought to investigate whether commercial banks are actually responsive to monetary policy. The study used an Error Correctional Model to estimate a relationship where lending rates were treated as the dependent variable while the independent variables were monetary policy, specifically CBR. The model was also expanded to include additional independent variables specifically monetary policy transmission channels. These include the credit channel which is represented by credit to the private sector, exchange rate channel represented as nominal exchange rate and asset price channel. For consistency, inflation and economic growth were included in the model because these are the targets of monetary policy. The study findings showed that there was a long run relationship between lending rates and Central Bank Rate, Exchange Rates, Asset Price, Credit to the Private Sector, Economic growth and Inflation Rates. The results also indicated that CBR and Inflation cause lending rates to increase in the short run while credit to the private sector causes lending rates to decrease in the short run. A statistically significant relationship was also established between lending rates and CBR, credit to the private sector. The study concludes that commercial banks' lending rates are indeed positively responsive to CBR and that in order to spur economic growth; commercial banks' lending rates should be stabilized by streamlining the economic environment in which commercial banks operate, therefore ensuring stable rates of borrowing.

Keywords: Monetary policy, Lending rates, Central Bank Rates, Credit Market, Commercial Banks

Introduction

Commercial banks' lending rates influence the availability of affordable funding for investment and consumption, therefore determining the overall rate of economic growth in an economy. When rates are high, people tend to shy away from borrowing because it will be difficult to pay back. Lower rates in any economy are beneficial because more people are likely to take loans in order to make purchases and expand their businesses, thus boosting economic growth. Monetary policy is one of the many factors that affect lending rates (Castro and Santos, 2010). Freixas and Rochet (2008) describe bank loans as important long-term financing sources in many countries, making banks the main mobilizers of financial resources and allocators of these resources to investments. In giving loans to their customers, banks are guided by profitability, liquidity and solvency principles, as well as the volume of deposits they hold, their investments, the prevailing interest rates, prestige, competition and public recognition (Olokoyo, 2011). In 2012, the Kenyan banking sector faced a tight monetary policy and a virtually slow rate of lowering their lending rates despite a considerable decline in the CBR in the second half of the year. Credit to the private

sector grew at a slower rate of 11.7 percent in 2012 compared to 30.8 percent growth in 2011 mainly due to the high cost of borrowing (Ministry of Devolution and Planning Report, 2013). Consequently, the country's banks have held home loan lending rates at between 17 and 19 percent in the past year (2013). Continuing high levels of interest rates have been stifling the local real estate market creating an obstacle to widespread home ownership, with home loan payments now running at typically twice prevailing rents, hence leaving business inventories with unsold property.

Reviewing Monetary Policy in Kenya and Lending Rates

The CBK is responsible for implementing monetary policy in Kenya in three main ways. First through Open Market Operations (OMO) whereby the Central Bank buys securities and increases the reserves of commercial banks thus enables them to lend more to their customers. This in turn increases the money supply in the economy. Secondly, monetary policy is implemented by the use of CBR which is defined as the lowest rate of interest charged on loans to commercial banks by the CBK and is the base for all monetary policy operations. CBR is determined by the MPC and its movement in direction and

magnitude signals the monetary policy stance. A reduction of the CBR shows an easing of monetary policy and a desire for market interest rates to move downwards. However, lower interest rates leads to an increase in the demand for credit which further spurs economic activities leading to growth. Thirdly, CBK uses CRR which is the share of a commercial bank's deposit liability which must be deposited at CBK at no interest. A reduction of the CRR improves commercial banks' liquidity thus enabling them to expand credit. An increase in CRR reduces liquidity and could also dampen demand-driven inflationary pressures. Lastly, CBK uses discount window operations where it provides short-term loans to commercial banks on an overnight basis at punitive rates, therefore making commercial banks seek funding in the market and using CBK funding only as a last resort. The discount rate is set by the Central Bank to reflect the monetary policy objectives of the time.

Lending rate, also interchangeably referred to as interest rate, is the fee that a borrower must pay to a lender to make up for the opportunity cost that the lender incurs in releasing and therefore not holding the borrowed funds. The various types of lending rates in Kenya are flat rate interest

which is based on the principal amount borrowed so that the interest charged remains constant until the term of the loan expires, and reducing balance interest rate which is based on the interest payable based on the principal balance remaining at each time interval, so that as the funds owing are repaid and decrease, so does the interest charged reduce. Fixed rates are interest rates that do not change throughout the term of the loan while Variable interest rates change during the term of the loan (Naheed *et al.*, 2009).

An Overview of Central Bank Rate and Credit Markets

Central Bank Rate (CBR) is the lowest interest rate that a Central Bank can charge on loans extended to commercial banks. This rate is reviewed by MPC and consequently announced every two months in Kenya (CBK, 2013). CBR was introduced in Kenya in June 2006 at an initial rate of 9.75, prior to which CBK operated under a monetary policy framework that included monetary aggregates targets that were consistent with a given level of inflation and economic growth. To date, CBK still uses a monetary programme that targets monetary aggregates. Monetary aggregate targeting has however been criticized as only being effective where there is a stable demand for

money relationship dependent on the overall economic activity and price level of a country – which may not be the case in Kenya (KIPPRA, 2006). CBR for decades has been employed in many countries as a tool of monetary policy (Mbotu, 2010). On the other hand, monetary policy transmission mechanisms explain how policy induced changes in the nominal stock or the short-term nominal interest rates have an impact on the economy. For instance the MPC changes the CBR from time to time to signal the monetary policy stance it is following (Were et al., 2013). According to Were, et. al., (2013) credit markets is vital as well as critical monetary policy transmission mechanism which works in two ways: first it affects the bank lending channel, and second, it affects firms' and households' balance sheets. For instance if central bank of Kenya lowers money stock, commercial bank's reserves fall leading to low supply of credit especially to the private sector. The reduction in money stock also leads to a fall in households' and firms' assets and equity prices, leading to a reduction in the net worth of borrowers. Banks then need to screen and monitor borrowers to avoid adverse selection and moral hazard. All these reduce the amount of lending that commercial banks are able to give hence

reducing domestic demand leading to a fall in total demand and eventually output (Were et al., 2013). Other transmission mechanisms include the asset price channel where monetary policy shocks result in fluctuations in assets prices (Agha et al., 2005); the interest rate channel where CBR influences other short-term rates and long-term interest rates, like the lending rate (Mishkin, 1995); the exchange rate channel where when domestic interest rates rise relative to foreign interest rates, equilibrium in the foreign exchange rate market would require gradual.

The biggest challenge Kenya is facing is the persistent increase in lending rates where the cost of borrowing has been rising incessantly. This has a negative effect on investment because the higher cost of borrowing discourages investors from borrowing capital. While the CBK has expended much effort to influence money supply by implementing various policies to curb inflation, there has been a general uproar this has not been felt on the ground because commercial banks have failed to respond in equivalence, especially where falling of rates is concerned. This study seeks to establish whether this is indeed true, and to measure the responsiveness of commercial bank's lending rates to changes

in the monetary policy stance, specifically the CBR. Further, there is limited information around the concept of the effectiveness of monetary policy in reducing lending rates and un-established impact of credit markets. This study therefore seeks to investigate whether there is an existence of a long run relationship between monetary policy and lending rates, thereby examining how monetary policy affects lending rates in Kenya and consequently offering the policy implication. The paper seeks to answer the following research questions: What is the contribution of monetary policy to lending rates in Kenya? Secondly what is the relationship between credit supply and commercial banks' lending rates in Kenya? The findings increases understanding fluctuations of commercial bank's lending rates as well as establish whether the CBK is fully responsible for this unsystematic change over time.

Literature Review

Keynesians believe that monetary policy transmission mechanisms are interest rates and investment. On the other hand the monetarists believe that monetary policy affects prices (interest rates included). It is argued that an expansionary monetary policy will decrease interest rates, increase

spending, increase aggregate demand and output and therefore decrease unemployment. But monetarists believe that expansionary monetary policy will affect mostly prices, not output related to increase in inflationary expectations and actually increase nominal interest rates. On the other hand, the classical theory of interest says that interest rate is determined by the supply of capital which depends on supply of capital on savings and the demand for capital for investment. The classical theory is based on the assumption that there is a direct relationship between the rate of interest, savings and direct relationship between interest and investment. In this case, high interest rates would lead to a high rate of savings and that investments would increase with a fall in interest rate (Satija, 2009). Similarly, loanable funds theory, includes saving out of current income, bank credit, dishoarding and disinvestments. The theory postulates that demand for funds arises for investment and hoarding wealth. Determination of interest rates under the loanable funds theory depends on the availability of loans which is based on the net increase in currency deposits, the amount of savings made and the willingness to enhance cash

balances and opportunities for the formation of fresh capital (Bibow, 2000).

According to liquidity preference theory, interest is the reward for parting with liquidity for a specified period of time. The theory claims that people have liquidity preference for the transaction motive, precautionary motive and speculative motive. It is pegged on the viewpoint that the rate of interest was determined by liquidity on the one hand and the supply of money on the other (Satija, 2009). Further, the loan pricing theory as advanced by Stiglitz and Weiss (1981) argued that banks are not in a position to set high interest rates in order to achieve the maximum interest income. This is because banks consider the possibility of the existence of adverse selection and moral hazard among their customers because it is challenging to predict the type of borrower at the beginning of the banking relationship. High interest rates tend to induce adverse selection problems by attracting high risk borrowers (Chodecai, 2004). It is therefore common to find that interest rates set by banks may not tally with the risk of borrowers.

Several studies suggest the presence of a bank lending channel of monetary policy in

several countries. The bank lending channel refers to the fact that changes in monetary policy influence the amount of loans disbursed by financial institutions.

Table 1: Empirical literature

Author and year	Type of study	Methodology	Results and conclusion
Aban (2013)	The relationship between loan growth and monetary policy	Ordinary least squares method (OLS)	Increasing policy rates results in a decrease the supply of loans in small banks and that smaller banks are more sensitive to monetary policy contractions than big banks.
Nguyen (2012)	The responsiveness of Vietnamese commercial banks to counter cyclical monetary policy.	Ordinary least squares method (OLS)	The study found that the asymmetrical response of Vietnamese commercial banks to countercyclical monetary policy was competitive and that the monetary authority was mostly successful in using its monetary policy instruments to achieve it's laid down objectives. The study recommended a strong political will and commitment by the authorities to reforming the current system while ensuring that frequent checks and balancing of the political environment as well as the banking system was in place.
Moinescu and Codirlasu (2011)	Explored the interaction between credit to the private sector and GDP growth in the new EU member states using annual data.	Panel data regressions	The persistence of a credit flow weaker than potential growth and excessive financing are associated with high levels of non-performing loans ratio two years later.
Aristei and Gallo (2012)	Determining the interest rate pass-through between interbank and retail bank interest rates in the Euro area using monthly data for the period 2003 – 2011.	Markov-switching vector autoregressive model	During financial distress, banks reduced their degree of pass-through from the interbank rate. Interest rates on loans to non-financial firms showed more responsiveness to changes in the interbank rate than loans to households, both in times of high volatility and in normal market conditions.
Maana and Tiriongo (2011)	Investigate the responsiveness of interbank interest rates and the 91 day Treasury bill rates to policy announcements.	Exponential generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity model	They found that monetary policy press releases were a sure way of directing the movement and direction of short term interest rates. They showed that announcements with loose policy inclination tend to be more effective compared with tight inclination.
Mohsin (2011)	estimate the impact of discount rate on weighted average lending and deposit rates in Pakistan using bank-type monthly data	Panel data technique followed by the Pedroni panel cointegration test	The study found that monetary policy effectiveness in Pakistan is limited and that there is a noteworthy lag in its completeness. Further, Georgievska et al. (2011) lending rates were largely determined by bank size, market share, deposit rates, non-performing loans as well as domestic policy rate and the foreign interest.
Olokoyo (2011)	Determinants of Nigeria's commercial banks' lending behaviour	ordinary least square estimation (OLS)	The study found that deposit base affect commercial banks' lending behaviour. The study concluded that banks should focus on mobilizing more deposits as this will enhance their lending performance. Banks were also advised to formulate solid financial plans.

Data and Methodology

Data Type and Source

This study used quarterly time series secondary data from the period of June 2006 to March 2014 because CBR was first introduced in June 2006. Quarterly data was therefore used to avoid the problem of limited degrees of freedom. Information collected includes; commercial bank's lending rates (dependent variable), CBR, Credit to the Private Sector (CPS), exchange rate, asset price, inflation and economic growth. This study focused on lending rates in general as charged by different banks where data relating to commercial banks' weighted average interest rates that correspond to each bank's market share in loans and advances was used. The data was collected from the CBK and World Bank.

Specification of the Model and Estimation Technique

The study used OLS to estimate a functional model where lending rates were treated as the dependent variable while the independent variables were monetary policy proxied by CBR because CBR is the instrument that mostly influences commercial banks' lending rates directly among all the other instruments of monetary policy and credit markets proxied by credit available to private sector which is

one of the main monetary policy transmission channel(s). This is because the main focus of the study was to determine the effect of monetary policy and credit supply on lending rates and to establish whether lending rates are actually responsive to monetary policy. Other credit transmission channels include; nominal exchange rate and Asset Price Channel. This paper considered both inflation and economic growth for consistency because these are the targets of monetary policy.

The functional relationship of the empirical model appeared as follows:

$$LR = f(CBR, CPS, NER, AP, In, Gr) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where: LR = Commercial banks' lending rates, CBR = Central Bank Rate, CPS = Credit to the private sector, NER = Nominal Exchange Rate, AP = Asset Price, In = Inflation and Gr is the Economic Growth.

This paper focused on the effect of monetary policy and credit market on commercial bank's lending rates. The variables NER, AP were included in the model because they are the transmission mechanisms of monetary policy; hence it was imperative to explore how these

transmission mechanisms affect lending rates. The model was estimated through ordinary least squares (OLS) and the relevant assumptions tested. In order to check for stationarity of the data, the study employed Augmented dickey fuller test (ADF). ADF was chosen here because it is usually not affected by autocorrelation as opposed to other tests. Similarly, cointegration test was conducted to establish the existence of long run or short run relationship between the lending rates and the respective explanatory variables through use of the Engel Granger test.

Data Analysis and Results

Descriptive Statistics

Lending rates (LR), Central Bank Rate (CBR), credit to the private sector (CPS), Exchange Rates (NER), Asset Price (AP), Inflation Rate (In) and Economic Growth (Gr) were summarized through computation of mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum. It was shown that all variables had 31 observations for the entire period of study whereby lending

rates had an average of 15.38% with a small standard deviation of 2.28% which fluctuated between the lows of 12.87% and the highs of 20.34% whereas the CBR oscillated within 6% and 18% but maintained a mean of 9.47%. Inflation rate showed a standard deviation of 5.41% from its mean of 8.74% which was close to its minimum value of 2.19% compared to its maximum value of 18.93% implying that most years had low inflation rates.

Trend analysis of Commercial Banks' Lending Rates

On commercial banks' lending rates trend as represented in Figure 1, statistics showed that the average lending rate in the 3rd quarter of 2006 was 13.63%, and 13.89% in the last quarter of the same year. The rates rose to 14.44% in the last quarter of 2008 and 14.88% in the second quarter of 2009. 2012 registered the highest lending rates by commercial banks: in the first quarter, the rate was 20.05%, the second quarter rate 20.21%, while the 3rd quarter rate was 20.00%. In the last quarter of 2013, lending rates had reduced to 16.95%.

Figure1. Commercial Banks' Lending Rates

Credit to the Private Sector

The results in Figure 2 below shows that, the amount of Credit to the Private Sector in the second quarter of 2006 was Ksh 428936 million which further rose to Ksh 519457 million in the 4th quarter of 2007. Credit to

the Private Sector continues to have an upward growth all through the five year period to register at Ksh 1555586 million in the last quarter of the year 2013.

Figure 2: Quarterly Credit to the Private Sector

Unit Root Test

Unit root tests are used to detect non stationarity in the study variables. If variables are non- stationary, their statistical properties tend to change over time, a characteristic which leads to spurious estimates. Therefore, if variables are found to be non- stationary, either successful

lagging is applied until the bias is eliminated or they are differenced. In our case, we undertook the first differences which rendered non stationary variables into stationary. The null hypothesis in this case was that the variable under consideration is non- stationary, that is has a unit root. The test results are in Table 2:

Table 2: Dickey-Fuller test for unit root

Variable	P Value at lag (0)	P Value at lag (0) After First Difference
LR	0.6285	0.0008
CBR	0.2852	0.0002
CPS	0.0005	-
NER	0.7444	0.0002
AP	0.5126	0.0001
In	0.3880	0.0370
Gr	0.0000	-

H₀: Variable has Unit Root

Table 2 shows that credit to the private sector and economic growth were stationary without any differencing while lending rates, central bank rate, exchange rate and inflation rate were stationary after first differencing. The model is therefore expressed as shown below;

$$DLR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DCBR_t + \beta_2 CPS_t + \beta_3 DNER_t + \beta_4 DAP_t + \beta_5 DIn_t + \beta_6 Gr + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

DLR = first differences of lending rates,
 DCBR = first differences of Central Bank Rate
 CPS= Credit to the Private sector,
 DNER = First difference of Annual exchange rate,
 DAP=first difference of Asset price,
 DIn= first difference of Inflation rate and
 Gr=Economic Growth

β 's 's are the coefficients to be estimated

ε_t is error term at time t.

The above model is now stationary implying it can be estimated after verifying all assumptions of OLS. If two or more variables are integrated of the same order and their differences have no clear tendency to increase or decrease then this will suggest that their differences are stationary. However, from Table 2, it was revealed that these variables were not integrated of the same order which implied that the study could not have proceeded to determine the long run relationship (cointegration). The study therefore regressed variables integrated of order on I(1) which included Central Bank Rate (CBR), Exchange Rates (NER), Asset Price (AP) and Interest Rates (IR).

Cointegration Test

Establishment of the existence of long run or short run relationship between the lending rates and the respective explanatory variables was necessary since most of the variables were integrated of order one except for credit to the private sector and economic growth. The Engel Granger test was used to test for cointegration. Having established stationarity, the study used a stationarity equation without those variables integrated of order zero, to generate the residuals and the first differences of the residual. The first differences, lagged values and lagged values of the first differences were included in the regression as model regressors (successive regression). The hypothesis tested in this case was that; H_0 : There is no Cointegration and H_1 : There is Cointegration. Table 3 shows the results;

Table 3: The Engle-Granger Test

D.uhat	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
uhat						
L1.	-0.0006768	0.0136795	-0.05	0.961	-.0287449	.0273912
LD.	0.1820169	0.1897597	0.96	0.346	-.2073379	.5713718
Number of Observations = 29 F(2, 27) = 0.46 Prob > F = 0.6360 R-squared = 0.0330 Adj R-squared = -0.0387 Root MSE = 1.1392						

Estimation of the Error Correction model

Among the core objective of this study were to estimate the responsiveness of commercial banks' lending rates to monetary policy in Kenya, to determine whether monetary policy transmission mechanisms have a significant relationship to commercial banks' lending rates in Kenya and lastly, to explore the effect of economic growth and inflation rate on lending rates in Kenya.

The estimated short run model includes the first lag of the error correction term despite the fact that the variables which were integrated of order one I(1) were not cointegrated as per the Engle-Granger test. The result that the ECM is highly significant suggested that the prior test used was weak. A long run relationship was established from the ECM. Table 5 illustrates the estimates of the ECM.

Table 5: Results for the Error Correction model

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Err.	z	P>z
D_LR				
ECT				
L1.	-0.004666***	0.00151	-3.09	0.000
LR				
LD.	0.3455572	7.550677	0.05	0.963
L2D.	-0.0164975	7.713804	-0.00	0.998
L3D.	0.7879534	6.040916	0.13	0.896
CBR				
LD.	0.0525448***	0.017514	3.00	0.001
L2D.	0.073547***	0.019612	3.75	0.000
L3D.	-0.2360445	1.72589	-0.14	0.891
CPS				
LD.	-0.3582445**	0.180022	-1.99	0.035
L2D.	0.5912762	17.29437	0.03	0.973
L3D.	0.7661291	10.20261	0.08	0.940
NER				
LD.	0.0057105	0.8220497	0.01	0.994
L2D.	0.0422126**	0.0181169	2.33	0.012
L3D.	-0.0006706	0.1731217	-0.00	0.997
AP				
LD.	-10.02665	36.85243	-0.27	0.786
L2D.	4.04864	33.59827	0.12	0.904

L3D.	-3.508451	28.34603	-0.12	0.901
In				
LD.	0.0685883**	0.0311765	2.22	0.023
L2D.	0.1267626***	0.0441681	2.87	0.002
L3D.	0.008876	0.3962775	0.02	0.982
Gr				
LD.	1.101966	4.348956	0.25	0.800
L2D.	1.254957	10.31345	0.12	0.903
L3D.	1.372939	15.47118	0.09	0.929
Constant	0.0969967	0.53774	0.18	0.857
R-Squared	0.7817			
chi2	14.32239			
P>chi2	0.0073			

Indicators (*/**/****) Significant at 1*, 5% and 10% levels

Table 5 shows that the coefficients of the first and second lag of the central bank rate, the first and second lags of inflation rates, second lag of exchange rates and first lag of credit to the private sector were highly statistically significant since their p-values were less than 0.05 and none of their confidence intervals included zero. On the same note, it was found that 78.17% of the variations in commercial banks' lending rate have been explained by Central Bank Rate (CBR), Credit to the private sector (CPS) Exchange Rates (NER), Asset Price (AP), Inflation Rates (In) and Economic growth (Gr). The rest of the variations were captured by the error term which represented factors not captured in the study, for example discount rates (Mohsin,

2011) and political atmosphere (Nguyen, 2012).

The model is as expressed below;

$$\begin{aligned}
 DLR_t = & 0.097 - 0.0047ECT_{t-1} + \\
 & 0.053DCBR_{t-1} + 0.074DCBR_{t-2} + \\
 & 0.358DCPS_{t-1} + 0.0422DNER_{t-2} + \\
 & 0.069DIn_{t-1} + \\
 & 0.127DIn_{t-2} \dots\dots\dots \\
 & \dots\dots(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where DLR = first differences of lending rates,

ECT_{t-1} = Error correction term at the first lag

DCBR_{t-1} = the first lag of the first differences of Central Bank Rate

DCBR_{t-2} = the second lag of the first differences of Central Bank Rate

$DCPS_{t-1}$ = the first lag of the first difference of the credit to the private sector

$DNER_{t-1}$ = the first lag of the first difference of Annual exchange rate

$DNER_{t-2}$ = the second lag of the first difference of Annual exchange rate

DIn_{t-1} = the first lag of the first difference of Inflation rate

DIn_{t-2} = the second lag of the first difference of Inflation rate

The above estimation shows that the dynamic stability was illustrated by the negative error correction term as -0.0047. This represents the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium that affects short run movement by the dependent variable. Also the negative sign agrees with the theory which indicates the backward move to equilibrium and the coefficient is less than the unit in absolute terms.

From the model above, it was found that the speed of adjustment was slow at 0.47% which implies that it can take quite a long time to return back to equilibrium in the long run. The first and second lags of CBR were positive and statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. This implied that there was a short run effect from CBR to lending rates with respect to these terms. However, the third lag of CBR was not

significant. In order to determine their joint effect, the study conducted Granger causality tests. The results revealed that the lagged terms of CBR jointly cause lending rates to increase in the short run. In addition, the second lag of exchange rates was positive and statistically significant at 5% significant level implying that a unit increase in exchange rate led to an increase in lending rates in the short run. However, the other lagged terms of exchange rates were not statistically significant. It was further revealed that there was a significant short run effect from the first and the second lagged term of inflation rates. The first and second lagged term of inflation rates demonstrated a positive and statistically significant relationship with lending rates while the third lag term was not statistically significant. Unlike the effect of inflation rates, the first lag of the credit to the private sector had a short run negative effect on lending rates whereby a unit increase in credit to the private sector caused a significant reduction in lending rates.

Further Discussion of the Results

As suggested earlier in the beginning of this study, commercial banks' lending rates affect the availability of affordable funding for investment and consumption. These two

key elements consequently have been termed as crucial in determining the overall rate of economic growth in an economy. It is suggested that if lending rates are high, people tend to shy away from borrowing. This study concentrated on exploring the factors determining commercial banks' lending rates with a key focus on the monetary policy represented by the CBR.

It was revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between commercial banks' lending rates and CBR. This implies that as the central bank rate increases, lending rate also increases. This finding concurs with the suggestions made by Maana and Tiriongo (2011) who found that monetary policy determined the direction of the movement of short term interest rates. They further argued that these monetary policies also have signalling power. It was also found by Aristei and Gallo (2012) that interest rates on loans to non-financial firms attracted more responsiveness to changes in the interbank rate than loans to households, both in times of high volatility and in normal market conditions. Considering Aban (2013) who investigated the relationship between loan growth and monetary policy in Philippines, it was revealed that increasing policy rates results in a decrease of the supply of loans in small

banks, which implies higher lending rates are instituted, and that smaller banks are more sensitive to monetary policy contractions than big banks. This blends well with our positive relationship between CBR and lending rate. On the other hand, Georgievska *et al.*, (2011) found that domestic policy rate and the foreign interest were also found to have a significant effect on the determination of lending rates. Therefore CBR is a significant factor determining lending rates.

Summary and Conclusions

The study findings showed that there was a highly significant long run relationship between commercial banks' lending rates and CBR, exchange rates, asset price, credit to the private sector, economic growth and inflation rates. The results also indicated that an increase in CBR, exchange rate, and inflation cause lending rates to increase in the short run while an increase in credit to the private sector cause lending rates to fall in the short run. A statistically significant relationship was also established between lending rates, exchange rate, CBR, credit to the private sector and inflation rate. The study also showed insignificant relationship between lending rates and asset prices as well as economic growth in short run. Based on the results and findings, the

study concludes that bank lending behaviour is indeed influenced mainly by CBR, credit to the private sector and inflation. The study therefore recommends that CBK should consider lowering CBR, which in turn could lead to decrease lending rates. The government should also consider streamlining the economic environment in which commercial banks operate, in order to help curb fluctuation in CBR which is an indication of the monetary policy stance and therefore ensure stable rates of borrowing. Stability of the lending sector reduces uncertainty which normally leads to non-performing loans. CBK implementing effective monetary policies that cushions borrowers will help curb speculative borrowing that affect lending behaviour by commercial banks.

The government through the central bank should also put in place measures to control sporadic changes in exchange rates. This will ensure that commercial banks' lending rates remain stable and favourable. Commercial banks and the CBK should also work hand in hand through close consultation and cooperation so that changes in the monetary policy stance are taken into account by commercial banks in their loan pricing decisions. They should consider striking a balance between

covering the costs associated with lending while simultaneously maintaining a good banking relationship with their borrowers, always keeping in mind that low cost of borrowing tends to lead to an increase in economic activities that spur economic growth. Finally, a fall in credit to the private sector however leads to a fall in demand in the economy hence leading to a fall in inflation. In as much as CBK may succeed in controlling inflation in this case, there exists a trade-off between growth and inflation. The main conclusion of this study is that CBR as an instrument of monetary policy is indeed an effective tool as it increases lending rates and relieves demand pull pressures on the economy. This could however conflict with the promotion of economic growth.

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